

Transition Metal Complexes of Heterocyclic Ligands. Part-II. Complexes of Some Schiff's Bases Derived from 2-furan Carboxaldehyde and Aromatic Amines

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The compound 2-furan carboxaldehyde reacts with aromatic amines such as aniline, *m*- and *p*-toluidines to form Schiff's bases (A) which function as bidentate ligands *in situ*, using the oxygen atom of furan ring and the imino nitrogen as the bonding sites, giving crystalline complexes of type $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2, \text{A}]\text{SO}_4$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4, \text{A}]\text{SO}_4$. These have been assigned planar and octahedral structures respectively on the basis of analytical, magnetic and spectroscopic data. A calculation of the ligand field parameters has also been made.

An extensive amount of work has been done on the Schiff's base complexes of transition elements, prepared by using a variety of aldehydes and amines. Almost no work has been reported on the Schiff's base complexes of 2-furan carboxaldehyde, although the free Schiff's bases formed between furfural or its derivatives and some arylamines have been studied thermo kinetically and qualitatively¹⁻⁵. In a previous communication we had reported complexes of free furfural with some metal(II) sulphates⁶. The present paper reports the preparation of six complexes of furfuraldimines with copper(II) and nickel(II) sulphates. The complexes have been fully characterised and their structures determined as outlined below.

Experimental

The complexes have been prepared *in situ* by mixing an equivalent amount of furfural (1 mole) and amine (1 mole), in methanol under stirring. A red coloured solution was obtained to which an calculated amount of metal(II) sulphate was added and the reaction mixture was further stirred for 8 hours. Heating makes the solution viscous and hence the stirring was done at room temperature. At the end of the period a crystalline complex was obtained, which was filtered, washed, dried and analysed.

The conductivities were measured on a Philips PR9500 magic eye type instrument. The magnetic moments were obtained by Gouy's method and the electronic spectra were measured in the form of solid samples on a VSU-2P spectrophotometer in the range 200-1400 nm.

Discussion

The Schiff's bases (A) prepared in the investigation are proposed to have the following structure

R = H, *m*-CH₃ or *p*-CH₃

and it is thus expected that coordination should take place from furan oxygen as well as azomethine link. The ligand is therefore bidentate in nature and should occupy any two adjacent positions in the coordination geometry of metal(II) ion.

The reaction with the ligand takes place only *in situ* and the parent Cu(II) & Ni(II) SO₄ which contain four and six coordinated water molecules are found to lose only two of these, irrespective of the time of reaction. Only one molecule of ligand is thus added and the other coordination sites are still occupied by water molecules.

Results of similar type were obtained during the studies on the ligand replacement reactions of some metal(II) sulphate complexes. Addition of ligands like aromatic amines, thiourea or furfural itself, led to the replacement of two water molecules, while the others could only be replaced by using stronger ligands like chelating diamines⁶⁻⁸. The analytical data of the present complexes (A) confirm that only one Schiff's base molecule has been added, and the other water molecules remain still attached to the metal.

The molar conductances of complexes (table 1) show that these behave as 1 : 1 electrolytes and hence the sulphate ion is not coordinated. The molecular formulæ of the complexes are thus $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{A}]\text{SO}_4$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4)\text{A}]\text{SO}_4$.

copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes in planar and octahedral environments respectively.

The diffuse reflectance spectra of all the complexes show one sharp band around 34.50 kK

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA

Complex no.	Complex	% metal	%C	%H	%N	%SO ₄	mhos	in B.M
1.	$\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{NO})\text{SO}_4$	17.26 (17.31)	36.25 (36.01)	3.62 (3.57)	3.45 (3.82)	26.90 (26.19)	305.6	1.856
2.	$\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{NO})\text{SO}_4$	14.82 (14.75)	32.96 (33.19)	3.15 (3.29)	3.62 (3.52)	24.84 (24.13)	312.6	3.452
3.	$\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(m\text{-C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO})\text{SO}_4$	16.45 (16.68)	37.50 (37.84)	3.72 (3.97)	3.86 (3.68)	25.01 (25.22)	302.8	1.872
4.	$\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(m\text{-C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO})\text{SO}_4$	14.05 (14.28)	34.86 (34.96)	3.95 (3.70)	3.46 (3.40)	23.21 (23.32)	310.5	3.483
5.	$\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(p\text{-C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO})\text{SO}_4$	16.28 (16.68)	37.62 (37.84)	3.75 (3.97)	3.40 (3.68)	25.62 (25.72)	—	1.842
6.	$\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(p\text{-C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO})\text{SO}_4$	14.10 (14.28)	34.56 (34.96)	3.72 (3.68)	3.60 (3.39)	23.59 (23.31)	307.0	3.043

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

Complex no.	Copper(II) complexes			Nickel(II) complexes			Dq in kK	in cm ⁻¹
	in nm	Energy in kK	Dq in cm ⁻¹	V ₁ in kK	V ₂ in kK	V ₃ in kK		
1.	760	13.16	1316	—	—	—	—	—
2.	—	—	—	919.1	13.51 12.82	25.00	919.1	947.9
3.	762	13.05	1305	—	—	—	—	—
4.	—	—	—	917.7	13.68 12.34	24.75	917.7	934.5
5.	770	12.98	1299	—	—	—	—	—
6.	—	—	—	9.132	13.88 12.34	25.02	913.2	904.2

In the infra red spectra of complexes (a) a strong broad band appears around 3410 cm⁻¹ assigned as the OH stretching and its negative shift is an indication of the coordination of water molecule⁹.

(b) Another very sharp and strong band is seen at 1630 ± 10 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes. This is the azomethine stretch, which in free ligand occurs at around 1600 cm⁻¹. This positive shift shows that its nitrogen atom is involved in coordination as found for many other Schiff's base complexes¹⁰⁻¹¹.

(c) Sharp bands at 1125 ± 5 and 630 ± 10 cm⁻¹ are due to the V₃ & V₄ modes of uncoordinated sulphate ion.

(d) A very sharp band at 500 ± 10 cm⁻¹, is clearly observed, which is the band involving the metal and furan oxygen¹²⁻¹³.

These data confirm the molecular formulæ of the complexes mentioned earlier. The magnetic moments of the complexes are in the usual range of one and two unpaired electrons as expected for

and another weak one at 22.75 kK. These bands have been observed in the spectra of many other Schiff's bases as well as their complexes¹⁴⁻¹⁵. The former corresponds to the perturbed benzene ring transition of amine fragment and later is due to the whole aromatic ring oriented trans with respect to double bond. There is an additional very broad band present in the spectra, the maximum for which has been approximated to lie around 1300 kK. This is the characteristic d-d transition of copper(II) in planar environment¹⁵, as the tetrahedral complexes usually give bands in the region lower than 10.00 kK^{16,17}. The broadness of the band is probably due to the presence of different ligands around the metal, which produce a ligand field of sufficiently low symmetry in complexes, thus causing severe distortion from the usual planar structure. The 10 Dq values for the complexes lie in the range 12,987-13,160 cm⁻¹ as expected for their planar geometry.

The nickel(II) complexes exhibit three transitions V₁, V₂ & V₃ characteristic of octahedral structure^{18,19}. These are seen around 9.20 ; 13.60 and 25.00 kK. The V₂ transition is broad and splits

into two components. This is a familiar phenomenon in such nickel(II) complexes which show distortions from octahedral structures due to the presence of dissimilar ligands in coordination sphere²⁰.

The V_1 transition is directly equal to Dq which comes around 920.0 cm^{-1} in the complexes, while the B values are around 925.0 cm^{-1} . These values are typical of distorted octahedral complexes of nickel(II)^{20,21}.

The Dq values of the parent ions i.e., $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$ are 1250 and 890 cm^{-1} . It thus appears that in these complexes, a ligand field of only slightly greater magnitude is being produced or the bidentate Schiff's base is only a moderately strong ligand than the water molecules. Hence it can be seen why only some of the water molecules and not all are being replaced, to give the complexes of type reported here.

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